

Oktabr, 2024-Yil

CLINICAL, MORPHOLOGICAL AND MOLECULAR FEATURES OF CHRONIC
ENDOMETRITIS IN WOMEN WITH INFERTILITY

Kurbaniyazova Aziza Zafarjonovna

Bukhara State Medical University Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology N 2

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13913773>

Research materials: Many scientists agree on the feasibility of complex two-stage therapy for CE [10, 16, 23, 25, 26]. The first step is to eliminate the infectious agent from the endometrium, which is achieved by prescribing broad-spectrum antibiotics aimed mainly against UPM. In a randomized placebo-controlled study, W. Andrews et al. [27] analyzed the dynamic changes in the composition of microorganisms in the endometrium in patients who received and did not receive AB treatment. The authors confirmed that the introduction of AB drugs significantly ensures the elimination of pathogens from the endometrium: UPM before treatment in 86% of cases, then in 37% ($p < 0.05$), without treatment these indicators were 91 and 60. % ($p > 0.05$) respectively. E. Cicinelli and others. [28] after performing hysteroscopy and prescribing AB therapy to patients with histologically confirmed CE, 71% of women showed complete normalization of hysteroscopic and morphological images of the endometrium and UPM was eliminated from the uterine cavity. managed to do q. 78.4% of patients in this group subsequently became pregnant. The authors concluded that antibiotic treatment for CE has beneficial effects in eliminating microorganisms from the endometrium and improving reproductive outcomes.

Object of the study: Absence of microorganisms or detection of lactobacilli / bifidobacteria in endometrial biopsy during cultural examination in women with a diagnosis of CE morphologically confirmed by local [6, 10, 16, 23, 25, 26, 29] and some foreign scientists. [30] is evaluated as the imperfection of the performed diagnostic measures. In such cases, as well as when it is impossible to carry out microbiological diagnostics, it is recommended to prescribe empiric AB therapy, taking into account the wide range of aerobic-anaerobic origin. AB treatment aimed at eliminating the infection helps to eliminate the clinical manifestations of the disease by normalizing the structural damage of the endometrium. AV Shurshalina, L. Eckert and others. [16, 18] showed that empirically prescribed antimicrobial therapy leads to a significant decrease in the frequency of uterine bleeding, restoration of the morphological structure of the endometrium in 57.1 and 89.5% of cases, respectively, and a decrease in the level is also observed. The main symptoms of inflammation.

Oktabr, 2024-Yil

Research results: in 2015, E. Cicinelli et al. [31] showed that CE treatment efficiency reached 83.3% in terms of normalizing the morphological picture of the endometrium when antibiotics were prescribed, taking into account the determined spectrum of microorganisms. According to the 2010 CDC recommendations [32], prescribing empiric therapy (ciprofloxacin in combination with doxycycline and metronidazole) to patients with conditionally sterile crops restored the morphological picture of the endometrium in only 46.2% of cases, although the patients were in this condition. This group was treated with three consecutive empirically determined treatment courses with AB drug changes. This study convincingly proves the need to find new diagnostic methods to more accurately assess the true microbial landscape of the uterine cavity.

In the office, the infectious agent plays a leading role in provoking the inflammatory process in the endometrium. In some cases, removal of the pathogen from the uterine cavity can occur without AB therapy [24, 27, 33]. In this case, microorganisms can leave secondary damage to the structure of the mucous membrane of the uterine cavity.

Conclusion: Modern literature discusses the role of AB drugs in changing the vaginal microsenosis with the formation of pathological associations of microorganisms, as well as in the accumulation of endotoxins and other microbial metabolites that contribute to the development of the inflammatory reaction of the macroorganism [33-36]. In 2006 [27], a clinical randomized placebo-controlled study was conducted including women with recurrent miscarriage and morphologically confirmed cholecystectomy. The study did not reveal any difference in the incidence of subsequent pregnancies in the groups of patients who received AB therapy (n = 52) and placebo (n = 56) - 53 and 59%, respectively. However, there was a tendency for the placebo group to prolong pregnancy by an average of 2.4 weeks and increase the weight of the newborns by an average of 418 g. The authors suggested the possibility of the development of microecological disorders in the vagina in response to AB therapy, which increases the risk of infection. Thus, prophylactic empiric prescription of antimicrobials with suspected CE is not always justified [27, 37, 38].

Recognizing the importance of AB therapy as a leading therapeutic approach to eliminate microbial agents from the site of inflammation, some authors believe that a similar result can be achieved using surgical approaches. In a clinical randomized placebo-controlled study, a number of scientists [27] examined 124 women with suspected CE who underwent hysteroscopy and diagnostic endometrial curettage to confirm the diagnosis. There were 2 groups: Group I (n = 59) received AB treatment, Group II (n = 65) received placebo. The effectiveness of the therapy was

Oktabr, 2024-Yil

evaluated based on the dynamics of plasma cells in the endometrium. The analysis of the results showed that AB therapy did not always help the treatment of CE with the normalization of the morphological appearance of the endometrium: in 22% of patients, plasma cells continued to be detected after treatment compared to 31% before prescribing antibiotics. ($p>0.05$). However, in the placebo group, the detection of plasma cells in the endometrium before and after treatment was 47 and 29%, respectively ($p>0.05$). Thus, AB therapy does not always normalize the morphological picture of the mucous membrane of the uterine cavity; however, only the use of hysteroscopy and diagnostic endometrial curettage has a positive effect on the loss of plasma cells. The presented results show that the mechanisms of spontaneous restoration of the morphological structure of the endometrium without the use of antibiotics remain unclear.

REFERENCES

1. Andryev S. et al. Experience with the use of memantine in the treatment of cognitive disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 282-288.
2. Antsiborov S. et al. Association of dopaminergic receptors of peripheral blood lymphocytes with a risk of developing antipsychotic extrapyramidal diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 29-35.
3. Asanova R. et al. Features of the treatment of patients with mental disorders and cardiovascular pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 545-550.
4. Begbudiyyev M. et al. Integration of psychiatric care into primary care //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 551-557.
5. Bo'Riyev B. et al. Features of clinical and psychopathological examination of young children //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 558-563.
6. Borisova Y. et al. Concomitant mental disorders and social functioning of adults with high-functioning autism/asperger syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 36-41.
7. Ivanovich U. A. et al. Efficacy and tolerance of pharmacotherapy with antidepressants in non-psychotic depressions in combination with chronic brain ischemia //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 409-414.
8. Nikolaevich R. A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 898-903.

Oktabr, 2024-Yil

9. Novikov A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 413-419.
10. Pachulia Y. et al. Assessment of the effect of psychopathic disorders on the dynamics of withdrawal syndrome in synthetic cannabinoid addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 240-244.
11. Pachulia Y. et al. Neurobiological indicators of clinical status and prognosis of therapeutic response in patients with paroxysmal schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 385-391.
12. Pogosov A. et al. Multidisciplinary approach to the rehabilitation of patients with somatized personality development //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 245-251.
13. Pogosov A. et al. Rational choice of pharmacotherapy for senile dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 230-235.
14. Pogosov S. et al. Gnostic disorders and their compensation in neuropsychological syndrome of vascular cognitive disorders in old age //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 258-264.
15. Pogosov S. et al. Prevention of adolescent drug abuse and prevention of yatrogenia during prophylaxis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 392-397.
16. Pogosov S. et al. Psychogenetic properties of drug patients as risk factors for the formation of addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 186-191.
17. Prostyakova N. et al. Changes in the postpsychotic period after acute polymorphic disorder //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 356-360.
18. Prostyakova N. et al. Issues of professional ethics in the treatment and management of patients with late dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 158-165.
19. Prostyakova N. et al. Sadness and loss reactions as a risk of forming a relationship together //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 252-257.
20. Prostyakova N. et al. Strategy for early diagnosis with cardiovascular diseaseisomatized mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 166-172.
21. Rotanov A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 267-272.

Oktabr, 2024-Yil

22. Rotanov A. et al. Diagnosis of depressive and suicidal spectrum disorders in students of a secondary special education institution //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 309-315.
23. Rotanov A. et al. Elderly epilepsy: neurophysiological aspects of non-psychotic mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 192-197.
24. Rotanov A. et al. Social, socio-cultural and behavioral risk factors for the spread of hiv infection //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 49-55.
25. Rotanov A. et al. Suicide and epidemiology and risk factors in oncological diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 398-403.
26. Sedenkov V. et al. Clinical and socio-demographic characteristics of elderly patients with suicide attempts //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 273-277.
27. Sedenkov V. et al. Modern methods of diagnosing depressive disorders in neurotic and affective disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 361-366.
28. Sedenkova M. et al. Basic principles of organizing gerontopsychiatric assistance and their advantages //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 63-69.
29. Sedenkova M. et al. Features of primary and secondary cognitive functions characteristic of dementia with delirium //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 56-62.
30. Sedenkova M. et al. The possibility of predicting the time of formation and development of alcohol dependence: the role of genetic risk, family weight and its level //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 173-178.
31. Shamilov V. et al. Disorders of decision-making in the case of depression: clinical evaluation and correlation with eeg indicators //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 198-204.
32. Solovyova Y. et al. Protective-adaptive complexes with codependency //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 70-75.
33. Solovyova Y. et al. Suicide prevention in adolescents with mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 303-308.
34. Solovyova Y. et al. The relevance of psychotic disorders in the acute period of a stroke //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 212-217.
35. Spirkina M. et al. Integrated approach to correcting neurocognitive defects in schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 76-81.